

Spatial integration and deployment coordination for firm wind generation

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Abstract

Wind power has considerable potential to decarbonise electricity systems due to its low cost and wide availability. However, wind variability limits its penetration. We propose a simple analytical framework to optimise the trade-off between achieving the maximum possible capacity factor (and thus minimum possible levelised cost) with the minimum possible variability (and thus integration costs). This framework is flexible enough to allow for near-optimal analysis, integration of demand, and consideration of additional decision criteria without additional modelling. We find that the intercontinental interconnection between China, Europe and the US with optimised capacity shares across regions could provide a firm generation profile with a capacity factor within the range 15%-40% for 99% of the time. Smaller-scale configurations corresponding to already existing electricity markets can also provide more certain and reliable generation profiles than individual regions in autarky.

Keywords

Energy transition, decarbonisation, transmission, variable renewable energy, wind power.

Wind power is one of the main instruments for decarbonising energy. It is already one of the lowest-cost sources of electricity^{1,2} with further cost declines expected³. Wind is expected to be the main source of electricity in 2050, accounting for 24% of global generation, according to the landmark Net Zero report by the International Energy Agency⁴. However, the variability of wind (and solar) output means clean firm technologies will be necessary to achieve rapid and cost-effective decarbonisation⁵. Wind variability poses challenges to its further diffusion: Grid constraints, institutional factors and oversupply cause wind curtailment at moments of peak generation⁶⁻⁹, the persistence of local low-wind events requires costly backup capacity or storage^{10,11}, and intermittency induces start-up costs to thermal power plants¹². This variability imposes integration costs to the electricity system¹³⁻¹⁶, and its impact on electricity prices results in revenue cannibalization which threatens the financial viability of variable renewables¹⁷⁻²⁰. Some solutions are already arising to address these problems. Storage and sector coupling could play a major role in renewables integration²⁰⁻²². Reducing the wind power inertia floor can reduce curtailment²³. Combining wind and solar provides complementarities²⁴. Geographic diversification²⁵ and internalizing the external costs²⁶ of fossil fuels can mitigate and even reverse the cannibalization effect. The effects of spatial integration have been studied from different perspectives²⁷⁻²⁹, but a robust global framework has not been developed to consistently quantify potential gains across major markets. Here, we propose such a global framework using the mean-variance framework, originally designed to obtain optimal investment portfolios in financial markets³⁰. Modern Portfolio Theory has been applied to energy markets, first to optimise fossil fuel procurement³¹ and later for a wide range of problems regarding technology selection and capacity allocation³². Particularly, this approach has been used to optimise wind allocation at different scales in Europe³³ and China³⁴.

We propose wind spatial integration and deployment coordination across regions to achieve a “firm” wind generation pattern that optimises the trade-off between achieving the maximum possible capacity factor with the lowest possible variability. We define “firm wind” as the capacity of wind power to achieve a given level of *reliability*, in the sense of ensuring a minimum generation level for most of the time (e.g. 95% of hours with a capacity factor above x), and *certainty*, understood as the concentration of the hourly capacity factor distribution around a central reference value (e.g. mean capacity factor ± 5 percentage points). We thus define “Firmness” as a quantifiable continuum rather than a discrete characteristic of electricity generation technologies³⁵.

Because demand also varies over time, achieving a flat generation profile is not ideal for integrating high shares of variable renewables. For this reason, we demonstrate how this approach can be applied not only to capacity factors, but also to the difference between demand and wind generation, i.e. residual load. Reliability and certainty in this case can be analogously understood as having the minimum possible residual load with the minimum possible variability. Because demand patterns are expected to change dramatically in the future with electrification, sector coupling, and demand response³⁶, we focus in the body of the paper on the first “firm wind approach” and illustrate in the Supplementary Information this second “load-following wind” approach with residual demand based on the latest available demand data³⁷.

Novel data and simple method

First, we derive a novel dataset of hourly capacity factors for wind farms for China, Europe and the US covering a period of ten years (2010–19). We combine wind speeds from the ERA5 global reanalysis dataset³⁸ with the Virtual Wind Farm model³⁹ (part of the Renewables.ninja platform⁴⁰) to generate profiles of power generation for all known wind farms (both onshore and offshore) operating within China, Europe and the US as of January 2020. We then aggregate these site-specific simulations to regional aggregates (countries for Europe, provinces for China and states for the US, hereafter referred simply as regions), and then validate and bias-correct the simulations using a bespoke database of reported wind capacity factors from government sources⁴¹, ensuring that the resulting capacity factors are representative of real-world productivity. The final dataset comprises ~10 million observations (89,280 hourly capacity factor values for 111 regions, 32 in China, 29 in Europe and 51 in the US, see Supplemental Information for summary statistics).

Then, we use these data to optimise the capacity factor-variability trade-off at different integration levels: (i) *subcontinental* level according to existing electricity markets and power regions, (ii) *quasi-continental* level (China, Europe, and the contiguous US (i.e. excluding Alaska and Hawaii)), and (iii) *intercontinental* level linking these three areas. We compare these results with individual regions in autarky.

Wind capacity factor (CF) is the ratio of actual to potential generation per unit of installed capacity, and variability is measured as the standard deviation (SD) of the hourly CF. We estimate the *portfolio*, i.e. the share of wind installed capacity per region, that minimises CF variability for each attainable mean CF for all considered spatial configurations. We show that

increasing the geographical scope of the optimised systems improves their CF-variability trade-off. The largest system, the intercontinental interconnection between China, Europe, and the US provides the highest potential benefits, but smaller systems at sub- and quasi-continental levels also provide considerable potential benefits over individual regions in autarky. In summary, spatial integration of regions with opposite generation patterns and deployment coordination of wind capacities provide a more reliable and certain aggregated generation pattern that can reduce curtailment, storage and backup capacity, enabling thus higher shares of wind power with lower integration costs.

Spatial integration and deployment coordination

Figure 1 shows the potential benefits of spatial integration and deployment coordination in optimizing the trade-off between high capacity factor and low variability at different integration levels. Grey dots indicate the mean CF and SD for each region in autarky at hourly level across the 10 years (2010-2019). The resulting CF determines the levelised cost of electricity (LCOE) for a given installation cost. The right vertical axes of Figure 1, panels A1-A3 show the range of LCOE assuming 2021 global weighted average onshore wind costs² and using the simplified LCOE calculation (see methods). Supplementary Figure 1 presents additional summary statistics including coefficients of variation ($CV = SD/\overline{CF}$) per region, showing that smaller regions usually present lower CF and higher CV because larger regions already benefit from some of the effects of spatial integration described below.

We define the subcontinental spatial configurations according to the existing electricity markets and power regions in China, Europe and the US (see the maps in Figure 1). We then optimise the portfolio of wind installed capacity for each configuration that minimises variability (SD) for each attainable level of CF. Figure 1 panels A1-A3 show the benefits of integration and coordination of each configuration at the sub- and quasi-continental levels with respect to regions in autarky. The efficient frontiers (coloured lines) represent the set of portfolios that minimise variability for each attainable mean capacity factor. The highlighted coloured point on each frontier represents the portfolio that optimises this trade-off in terms of achieving the maximum possible mean capacity factor per unit of variability, i.e. the reciprocal of the coefficient of variation ($CV^{-1} = \overline{CF}/SD$). Whereas this portfolio is the technical optimum, this approach provides decision-makers room to move along the frontier to keep efficient configurations depending on their preferences regarding the levels of CF (determining LCOE) and variability (determining integration costs), as well as other potential complementary capacity allocation

criteria. This framework also provides the feasible space below the efficient frontier to assess second-best options along the lines of the near-optimal energy modelling reasoning⁴².

Figure 1. Spatial integration and deployment coordination improve the capacity factor-variability trade-off with respect to any single region in autarky. Panels A1-A3: grey points indicate the mean capacity factor and variability (measured as the standard deviation of the hourly capacity factor) for each Chinese province, European country and US state in autarky. Lines represent the efficient frontiers, where each point along the frontier is a portfolio of shares of installed wind capacity per region with the minimum possible variability for each mean capacity factor. The highlighted points along the frontiers indicate the optimal portfolio (defined as the maximum mean capacity factor per unit of variability). The assumptions for the calculation of the levelised cost of electricity (LCOE in USD/MWh, right axis) are \$1,325/KW installation cost, \$40/KW yearly operation and maintenance cost, 25 years lifetime and 5% interest rate. Note that the panels have different axes scales and the relation between CF (left axis) and LCOE (right axis) is nonlinear. Panels B1-B3 give the optimal portfolio for each sub-continental configuration, and panels C1-C3 give the optimal quasi-continental configurations. In panels B1-B3, each power region is represented by a different colour and surrounded by a thick border, and the colour intensity of each region (province, country or state) represents the share of wind installed capacity relative to the larger power region to which it belongs. See Supplementary Figure 2 for the minimum variability portfolios and Supplementary Figure 6 for the analogous analysis of residual load instead of capacity factor.

The lower-left corner of the frontier is the portfolio with the lowest possible variability. As we move up and rightwards along the frontier, we prioritise higher capacity factor over lower variability up to the maximum possible capacity factor at the top right of the frontier. The

decision of where to move along the curve will ultimately depend on the balance between the cost of variability and the value of generation. This is a fertile avenue of further research to expand this approach depending on different cost/value assumptions or additional capacity allocation criteria and constraints. For now, we focus on the technical optimum (i.e. the maximum attainable mean capacity factor per unit of variability), as it provides the foundations to achieve a firm wind generation pattern that provides high levels of reliability and certainty.

Whereas we focus here on the technical optimum (point along the frontier), any portfolio of shares along the efficient frontier can be obtained from the code and data made available by the authors (see data availability section). Supplementary Figure 2 shows the installed capacities for the minimum variability portfolio (bottom-left corner of the efficient frontier). In this case, capacities are located in the regions with opposite generation patterns to achieve the flattest possible aggregate generation profile.

The efficient frontiers in panels A1-A3 of Figure 1 show that even small configurations at sub-continental level provide significant benefits in terms of higher capacity factors and lower variability compared to individual regions in autarky. These configurations are relatively easier to implement in reality because these power regions already have some level of integration. Continental-scale integration and coordination is always better than smaller sub-continental configurations. The case of Mibel (the Iberian Electricity Market) exemplifies the basic functioning of this framework. Since it comprises only two countries (Portugal and Spain), the frontier is roughly a line between both countries (representing all possible capacity allocation options between both countries), and the benefits from integration and coordination are limited because both countries have similar generation patterns. As the configurations become larger and more diverse in terms of generation patterns, the efficient frontiers shift left and upwards, indicating lower variability and higher capacity factor, respectively, and thus higher potential gains. The maps in Figure 1 show the optimal shares of wind installed capacity for the sub-continental (panels B1-B3) and quasi-continental (panels C1-C3) configurations.

The same analysis can be replicated with residual load (total demand minus wind generation) instead of capacity factor. In this case, we minimise both residual load and its variability. For this reason, the efficient frontiers are now concave, but the interpretation is analogous. Supplementary Figure 6 shows the equivalent results of Figure 1 for residual load instead of capacity factor. This approach has the advantage of providing capacities that mimic demand patterns, but the disadvantage that current demand patterns are not representative of future

ones. It is also harder to see the benefits of spatial integration and deployment coordination because the results confound the effect of aggregating both generation and demand profiles.

Intercontinental interconnection

Figure 2 shows that an intercontinental interconnection linking China, Europe and the US would provide additional benefits to optimise the capacity factor-variability trade-off. Recent studies show the feasibility of intercontinental interconnections with ultra-high-voltage (UHVDC) transmission lines⁴³ and multiple projects are currently being planned (e.g. Xlinks between Morocco and the UK or the Australia-Asia Power Link). Panel A shows that the intercontinental configuration achieves lower variability for each level of capacity factor compared to the continental efficient frontiers also depicted in Figure 1 panels A1-A3. The upper part of the intercontinental frontier overlaps with the US because the region with the highest capacity factor (Nebraska) is in the US and thus capacity tends to relocate there as the portfolio prioritises higher capacity factor over lower variability.

Although China has lower wind resources than the US on average (see Supplementary Figure 1), its territory comprises more diverse wind patterns, and therefore its optimal portfolio has lower variability and capacity factor than that of the US. Europe has the worst wind resources of the three continents in terms of the capacity factor-variability trade-off (due in part to its smaller land area), and hence would have the largest benefits from spatial integration and deployment coordination. The bars in Figure 2 panel A show the capacity allocation of the three extreme portfolios (lowest variability in the bottom left of the curve, highest CF in the top right, and optimal—highlighted point). In the highest CF portfolio all the capacity is simply installed in the region with the highest CF of the dataset: Nebraska. Both the optimal and the lowest variability portfolio have relatively even distributions of capacities across the three continents with continental shares ranging between 27-41% each.

Figure 2. Intercontinental interconnection improves the capacity factor-variability trade-off more than any other configuration. Panel A: efficient frontiers (lines) and optimal portfolios (points) for each quasi-continental and the intercontinental configuration. Each point along the frontier represents a portfolio (shares of wind installed capacity per region) with the minimum possible variability for each attainable mean capacity factor. The bars represent the distribution of capacities across continents in the intercontinental configuration for the three extreme portfolios: minimum variability, optimal, and maximum CF. Panel B: capacity factor cumulative probability distribution for each configuration and selected regions. Spatial integration and deployment coordination shifts the cumulative probability to the right minimizing the probability of low-wind events and increases its slope entailing capacity factors more concentrated around central values. Panel C: optimal portfolio for the intercontinental configuration. See Supplementary Figure 3 for cumulative probabilities of all subcontinental configurations, Supplementary Table 1 for the summary statistics of the optimized generation profiles for all configurations, and Supplementary Figures 7 and 8 for the analogous analysis of residual load.

The capacity factor cumulative probability distributions (Figure 2.B) show how optimised portfolios improve certainty and reliability, achieving thus firmer generation profiles. The slope of the cumulative probability distribution shows how concentrated hourly capacity factors of the optimal portfolios are around the central values, showing therefore how certain its generation pattern is. Likewise, reliability is the capacity to provide a minimum level of generation all or most of the time. Cumulative probability distributions that start flat at 0 and are more displaced to the right are more reliable because the probability of low capacity factors is lower. For instance, Nebraska's capacity factor interquartile range is 23-67%. While its mean capacity factor is high (45%), its generation pattern is uncertain due to a large interquartile

spread (43 percentage points (p.p.)), and unreliable because the capacity factor is lower than 10% almost 9% of the time. In the other extreme, Switzerland has a certain but unreliable generation pattern. Wind spatial integration and deployment coordination across the contiguous US would improve both certainty (interquartile range spread declines to 12 p.p. [24-36% CF]) and reliability (capacity factor lower than 10% only 0.4% of the time), at the cost of a lower mean capacity factor (30%). An intercontinental configuration improves reliability and certainty even further, achieving a CF between 15%-40% for 99% of the time (interquartile range spread of only 7 p.p. (23-30% CF) and a minimum capacity factor of 9%). Thus, even regions with high mean capacity factors can benefit from spatial integration and deployment coordination (See Supplementary Table 1 for the summary statistics of the optimized generation profiles for all configurations).

The map in Figure 2 panel C shows the optimal allocation of wind capacity across regions in the intercontinental configuration. This portfolio of wind installed capacities maximises the mean capacity factor per unit of variability, providing the most certain and reliable wind profile possible. For this reason, capacity is allocated to regions that have high capacity factor and complementary wind profiles with other regions within the system. Many regions do not have any installed capacity because other regions have both higher capacity factors and more complementary wind patterns. Minimum and maximum constraints could be exogenously set to produce more evenly distributed and politically feasible results at the cost of a lower CF-variability outcome.

Firm wind

We define the “firmness” of wind power as the capacity to provide the highest possible level of reliability and certainty. One way to illustrate these definitions is by plotting their cumulative distributions as in Figure 2. To assess the implications of our results we further operationalise these definitions by specifying *reliability* as the capacity to provide a minimum capacity factor for 95% of the time, and *certainty* as the probability of capacity factors within the range of the mean capacity factor ± 5 percentage points (these values are arbitrary to resemble the conventional 5% significance levels commonly used in statistics, but any other value could be used, see Supplementary Figure 4 for the same illustration with the levels of 1%/ ± 1 pp and 10%/ ± 10 pp). Figure 3 shows the level of firmness for each region in autarky (grey) and configuration according to these definitions. Individual regions in autarky provide low reliability and certainty (lower-left corner), but as regions integrate and coordinate capacity deployment,

reliability and certainty increase (upper-right corner) until achieving 95% of hours with a capacity factor above 19% and 70% of hours with a CF within the range 21-31% (26% mean \pm 5p.p.).

Figure 3. Spatial integration and deployment coordination improve wind reliability, measured as the minimum capacity factor (CF) achieved 95% of the time (i.e. the 5th percentile of CF), and certainty, measured as probability of CF within the range of mean \pm 5 percentage points. See Supplementary Figure 4 for the same figure at other levels of reliability and certainty, and Supplementary Figure 9 for the analogous analysis of residual load.

Finally, Figure 4 compares the resulting aggregate generation profiles (10-year average and standard deviation) of the optimised portfolios (left column) with selected regions in autarky (right column). The first row shows the optimal intercontinental wind generation profile compared to Switzerland, the region with the lowest variability of the dataset. The optimal intercontinental profile provided both a higher mean capacity factor and lower variability than even the region with lowest variability. The other rows compare the optimal quasi-continental portfolios with the region with the highest capacity factor of each region. The optimal quasi-continental profiles will have, by definition, a lower mean capacity factor than the region with the highest capacity factor of each configuration, but in return have a much “firmer” generation profile that resembles a baseload technology.

Figure 4. Capacity factor profiles of the optimised intercontinental and quasi-continental configurations (left column) compared to the region with lowest standard deviation of the dataset (Switzerland), and with the regions with the highest capacity factor within each quasi-continental configuration. The solid line is the 10-year average and the shaded area is the standard deviation. See Supplementary Figure 10 for the analogous analysis of residual load.

Discussion

We show that wind spatial integration and deployment coordination can bring substantial benefits in optimizing the trade-off between high capacity factors and low variability. This can

help mitigate integration costs and the cannibalization effect, and reduce the need for backup capacity and curtailment. Wind power can provide a considerable level of “firmness”, defined as combination of *reliability* (a minimum level of generation most of the time) and *certainty* (capacity factor distribution concentrated around a central value).

The main advantage of this approach is its simplicity and flexibility. Simplicity because it only requires data on hourly CF and a basic optimization method. With the proposed definitions of reliability and certainty, this approach allows us to compare the “firmness” of different portfolios (shares of installed capacities across countries) and the potential gains from system integration and deployment coordination. Flexibility because it allows the comparison between many different portfolios, optimal (maximum CF per unit of variability), efficient (along the frontier) or other near-optimal (below the frontier) alternatives. We additionally show in the Supplementary Information how demand can be integrated in this analysis, such that we minimise residual load (difference between demand and wind generation), instead of maximising CF. Whereas this is a promising approach, as it allows for “load-following” wind power rather than just “firm”, current demand patterns are likely not representative of future ones, and that is why we focus on the first approach. However, this residual demand approach could be interesting for prospective studies that also model future demand patterns.

Practically achieving the proposed levels of international interconnection and coordinated deployment, however, depends on both institutional factors and the costs of spatial integration (mainly interconnections), compared to alternative flexibility options, such as storage, demand management or zero-carbon dispatchable technologies. Spatial integration has co-benefits related to the integration of other variable renewable energy technologies (mainly solar), the balance of different consumption patterns and grid resilience more generally, but also risks associated with energy interdependence between countries. Further research should take all these aspects into account to assess the economic and political feasibility of international interconnections. Plans in this direction are already being discussed in China⁴⁴, Europe⁴⁵ and the US⁴⁶.

Methods

Wind speeds and power outputs

Wind speeds at 10 and 100m above ground were extracted from the ERA5 reanalysis³⁸. This was chosen over MERRA-2 as it is derived from a more recent model that assimilates more weather

observations and delivers data with higher spatial resolution (0.25 x 0.25 degrees). Wind speeds at each timestamp and grid point were transformed into a log-law wind profile, which can infer wind speed, w , at any given turbine hub height, h , via:

$$w_h = A \log\left(\frac{h}{z}\right)$$

where A is the wind shear and z the surface roughness, derived from regression of the ERA5 wind speed data³⁹. The resulting wind speeds were then interpolated spatially from the regular ERA5 grid to the location of individual wind farms using a non-smoothing spline.

Reanalysis has been shown to have bias in its wind speeds, which is reasonably stationary over time but heterogeneous across space^{41,47}. This means that while the pattern of wind farm production can be considered accurate, the long-term average level of production needs to be corrected according to the location. We apply a linear correction factor to wind speeds such that the resulting capacity factors match the observed long-run average at country, province or state level⁴¹. The correction combined a linear offset and multiplicative scale factor to provide an acceptable compromise between simplicity (thus avoiding over-fitting) and representing the seasonal and hourly variability across the regions studied.

Modified wind speed, w' , was calculated from raw wind speed, w , and the bias – or systematic error – in capacity factors, which is defined as the ratio of observed to simulated capacity factors, CF :

$$w' = \left(0.6 \frac{CF_{obs}}{CF_{sim}} + 0.2\right) w + \beta$$

For each individual wind farm, the VWF model uses a simple iterative process to seek a value for linear offset term, β , so that the farm's long run average capacity factor is scaled by the desired bias correction factor, $\frac{CF_{obs}}{CF_{sim}}$. The ratio of multiplicative and additive components (0.6 and 0.2 in the above equation) are taken from previous work⁴¹.

Wind speeds were converted to power outputs using empirical power curves that were collected for 140 models of wind turbine⁴⁰. These curves were smoothed using a Gaussian kernel to account for the distribution of wind speeds experienced within any given hour, and between the individual turbines of a specific farm⁴¹.

Wind farm simulations

We modelled all wind farms that were known to be operating in each region we consider as of January 2020. For this, we took the location (latitude and longitude), hub height (in metres), installed capacity (in MW) and the model of wind turbine for each farm from The Wind Power database⁴⁸. This yielded 1,180 wind farms in China, 1,442 in the US and 19,979 in Europe.

Missing metadata for these farms were inferred where possible. Latitude and longitude data were missing for 5% of farms (14% in China, 2% in the US, 5% in Europe). These were inferred by geolocation where the nearest county or city was known using the Bing Maps Locations API (<https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/bingmaps/rest-services/locations/>). Hub height data were missing for 37% of wind farms (80% in China, 26% in the US and 35% in Europe). These were inferred by stochastically sampling other wind farms with known heights that use the same turbine model in the same country or neighbouring countries if none were available. Turbine model was not known for 20% of wind farms (11% in China, 21% in the US and 20% in Europe). These were inferred by stochastically sampling other wind farms with similar capacity, average estimated wind speed and construction date in the same country or neighbouring countries if none were available.

Despite simulating the output of over 20,000 wind farms, there were some regions in this study with limited coverage; for example, no wind farms were specified in the US states of Alabama, Louisiana or Florida. We therefore randomly generated hypothetical wind farms in any region which contained less than 20 wind farms, and add these to the known farms so that at least 20 sites were modelled within each region. These farms were randomly placed within the zone, with randomly selected turbine model and hub height sampled from other farms within the country or neighbouring countries. They were given a negligible capacity (1 MW) so their output would only affect regions with little to no existing wind farms, and thus add some geographical diversity to their regional aggregate.

The resulting wind farm simulations were aggregated to give the time series of total power output at national level in Europe, state level in the US and provincial level in China. The GADM dataset level 0 and level 1 were used to define the shapefile for each region. One exception to this was that the Chinese province of Nei Mongol (Inner Mongolia) was further separated into an eastern and western region due to its importance for wind power production and physical size (spanning almost 30 degrees of longitude). This split was defined by banner/county-level administrative divisions, with those to the west of Abag and Plain Blue defined as West Nei Mongol, and those east of (and including) them as East Nei Mongol.

Validation and bias correction

We update previous bias correction factors for European countries⁴¹ and replicate their calculations for Chinese provinces and US states. Bias correction factors for all regions are given in the Supplementary Information. For Europe, hourly metered wind farm output was collected from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform (<https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>) and national transmission system operators (TSOs) in 12 countries, plus annual-average capacity factors derived from IRENA (<https://irena.org/Statistics>) for the remaining countries.

The only public data found for China were annual average capacity factors for each province, published by the National Energy Administration from 2013 to 2019 (http://www.nea.gov.cn/2020-02/28/c_138827910.htm). Wind farm curtailment due to grid constraints is an important consideration, as this amounted to 17% of all wind power production across China in 2016, falling to 4% in 2019 (http://www.nea.gov.cn/2020-02/28/c_138827910.htm). This was removed from the data to give gross capacity factors (i.e. what could have been attained given the prevailing meteorological conditions).

Monthly-average capacity factors were derived for US states from the Electric Power Monthly dataset published by the Energy Information Administration (<https://www.eia.gov/electricity/data/state/>). This covered 36 states which had at least 10 MW of wind capacity installed and at least three years of reported data.

Modern Portfolio Theory

We apply Modern Portfolio Theory to assess the trade-off between capacity factor and variability (measured as standard deviation) for wind generation. We use the hourly wind capacity factor data for each region during 10 years presented above. The problem consists in minimizing the portfolio standard deviation (σ_p) for the attainable range of average capacity according to eq. (1):

$$\min(\sigma_p) = \min\left(\sqrt{\sum_i w_i^2 \sigma_i^2 + \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} w_i w_j \rho_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j}\right) \quad (1)$$

where the first addend is the sum of variances (σ_i^2) times the squared shares of wind installed capacity in each country (w_i^2) and the second addend is the covariance of hourly capacity factor between regions and their correlation ρ_{ij} . This minimization is subject to a non-negativity constraint (i.e. all shares must be positive or zero: $w_i \in \mathbb{R} \geq 0$), and a “full investment”

constraint (i.e. the sum of shares must equal one, $\sum w_i = 1$). This process is iterated for all attainable levels of the capacity factor, such that each iteration includes the constraint that the portfolio capacity factor must be equal to a value exogenously set ($\sum \frac{w_i \overline{CF}_i}{w_i} = CF$). The result of this optimization exercise is a set of efficient portfolios that have the minimum possible variability for each attainable mean capacity factor. Each portfolio is the relative distribution of wind installed capacities across regions, as shown in the maps in Figures 1 and 2. Finally, we obtain the optimal portfolio for each configuration as the one that maximises the mean capacity factor per unit of variability, which is the inverse of the coefficient of variation: $CV^{-1} = \overline{CF}/SD$.

Levelised cost of electricity

The levelised cost of electricity (LCOE) in Figure 1 panels A1-A3 is calculated with the simplified formula:

$$LCOE = \frac{IC \cdot CRF + O\&M}{CF \cdot 8760}$$

$$CRF = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1}$$

Where CRF is the capital recovery factor depending on the interest rate i (assumed 5%) and the lifetime of the system n (assumed 25 years). The installation cost (IC) is assumed to be \$1,325/kW corresponding to the global weighted average as reported by the latest IRENA cost report². IRENA reports operation and maintenance costs ranging between 33-50 \$/kW annually, so we assume an intermediate value of \$40/kW per year. The capacity factor (CF) is the corresponding value at each level in Figure 1.

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Competing Interests statement

The authors declare no competing interests.

Code and data availability

The replication package including code and data is available at Zenodo:

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Supplementary Information

This Supplementary information is divided in four sections. Section 1 presents additional figures related to the main analysis. Section 2 replicates the main results of the paper integrating demand, i.e. optimizing the trade-off between residual load and variability, instead of CF-variability. Section 3 shows the bias correction factors used to generate the new CF data. Section 4 summarizes the regional configurations and naming conventions.

1. Additional figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Summary statistics: mean capacity factor (left) and coefficient of variation (right) for each region of each continent.

Supplementary Figure 2. Minimum variability portfolios tend to allocate wind capacity in regions opposite generation patterns. See Figures 1 and 2 in the body for the optimal portfolios.

Supplementary Figure 3. Capacity factor cumulative probability distributions for the optimal portfolios of each quasi- and sub-continental configuration in China (left), Europe (centre) and the US (right). See Figure 2 for the intercontinental cumulative probability distribution.

Supplementary Figure 4. Firm wind plot at 1 and 10 levels of reliability (percentage) and certainty (percentage points). See Figure 3 for the same figure at 5 level.

Region	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
Epex Spot	1.85	15.54	23.2	25.33	32.98	86.41
Nord Pool	0.86	17.56	25.7	28.08	36.26	84.44
Mibel	0.56	12.78	21.26	25.29	33.73	90.81
WECC	2.25	22.46	30.88	32.14	40.81	85.38
MRO	1.54	27.83	38.74	39.86	50.77	92.36
SERC	0.24	13.93	20.98	22.12	29.26	70.89
RF	0.13	16.13	26.97	29.69	40.73	91.97
NPCC	0.33	15.27	24.73	28.02	38	92.39
Northwest	1.93	15.48	22.45	24.24	31.09	78.55
Central	0.3	13.27	21.53	23.69	32.07	82.71
South	0.15	13.61	21.26	21.84	29.13	68.57
East	0.17	17.98	26.08	27.06	34.87	80.18
Northeast	1.06	14.71	21.92	23.35	30.31	77.8
Europe	4.74	18.88	23.89	24.96	30.29	61.61
US	5.46	23.95	29.87	30.31	36.26	65.91
China	5.04	19.86	24.28	24.69	29.11	57.51
Intercontinental	9.26	22.97	26.2	26.39	29.57	47.29

Supplementary Table 1. Summary statistics of the resulting capacity factor profile (%) for the optimized portfolios of the sub-, quasi- and inter- continental configurations.

2. Residual load

In this section we replicate the analysis presented in the body of the paper, using the trade-off between residual load and variability, rather than capacity factor-variability. Minimizing residual load and variability would in principle be preferable than just maximising CF for each level of variability because we integrate demand patterns in the analysis. Thus, we would have “load-following” wind power, because the model minimises residual load, rather than just “firm wind”

when the model maximises capacity factor. However, these empirical results are not likely to hold in the future as demand patterns are expected to change dramatically due to electrification, sector coupling and demand flexibility. For this reason, we illustrate here the approach with current available demand data for 2019³⁷, but further research should derive long-term empirical results with future demand patterns. Demand data for the US are not available at the state level, but only for 13 regions (California, Carolinas, Central, Florida, Mid-Atlantic, Midwest, New England, New York, Northwest, Southeast, Southwest, Tennessee and Texas). We aggregate them at the power region level such that WECC comprises California, Northwest and Southwest, SERC includes Carolinas, Florida, Southeast and Tennessee), RF corresponds to Mid-Atlantic, NPCC is formed by New England and New York and ERCOT is Texas. Finally, because the Midwest region belongs to multiple different power regions, we assigned the population-weighted shares of demand to each power region, such that (i) Louisiana, Arkansas, Missouri and Illinois, accounting for 45.9% of the total Midwest region, are assigned to SERC, (ii) Indiana and Michigan, accounting for 28.9% of the total, are assigned to RF, and (iii) Iowa, Wisconsin and Minnesota, accounting for 25.2% of the total, are assigned to MRO. For this reason, autarky results for US states are omitted from this analysis.

We first express demand (D_t) in terms of peak load for each region to have comparable results across regions with very different scales. Then we calculate hourly residual load (RL_t) as the difference between demand (expressed as a share of peak load) and the capacity factor (CF_t). This is equivalent to assuming that we install the same wind capacity as peak load. Thus, positive RL values mean residual loads that should be met by other means, and negative ones mean that wind generation is higher than load.

$$RL_t = \frac{D_t}{\max(D_t)} - CF_t$$

We replicate this process for all configurations, such that we first aggregate demand within the system and then calculate the peak and residual loads. The problem is then analogous as with the capacity factor: we want to find the efficient frontier of portfolios that provide the minimum possible portfolio variability for each level of attainable residual load (see Methods section). Supplementary Figure 5 shows the resulting average residual demand for each region of each

continent and coefficient of variation in autarky. The negative value for Estonia means that if Estonia installed as much wind capacity as its peak load, it would have an average of 20% excess generation. Positive values means the remaining residual load, that could be met by other means or by installing more capacity than the peak load.

Supplementary Figure 5. Summary statistics: mean residual load (left) and coefficient of variation (right) for each region of each continent. US omitted due to the lack of state-level data.

Supplementary Figure 6 shows the efficient frontiers of the quasi- and sub-continental configurations, analogous to Figure 1. Here the frontiers are downward sloping because optimal portfolios minimise both variability and residual load, rather than maximising CF. Additionally, we define the optimal portfolio as the one with the lowest product of residual load and variability (instead of the one with highest capacity factor per unit of variability, because we now want to minimise both residual load and its variability). The following figures in this section replicate the main analysis for the residual load (instead of capacity factor) framework.

Supplementary Figure 6. Residual load efficient frontiers (as % of peak load) for (1) China, (2) Europe and the (3) US. Grey dots represent regions in autarky. Lines show the efficient frontier of portfolios with the minimum possible variability for each level of residual load. The highlighted point on the frontiers shows the portfolio with the lowest product of residual load and variability (analogous to Figure 1).

Supplementary Figure 7. Continental and intercontinental efficient frontiers (A), cumulative probability distributions (B) and intercontinental optimal capacity shares (C) (analogous to Figure 2)

Supplementary Figure 8. Cumulative probability distributions for the optimal portfolios of the quasi- and sub-continental configurations in China (left) and Europe (centre). The US (right) sub-continental configurations are not optimised because there is no demand data at the state level (analogous to Supplementary Figure 3).

Supplementary Figure 9. “Load-following wind”: reliability and certainty of the residual load for regions in autarky (grey) and the optimal portfolios of each configuration at 1, 5 and 10 levels. The axes are inverted to keep the aesthetics of the Figure 4 and Supplementary Figure 3.

Supplementary Figure 10. Demeaned residual load profiles of the optimised intercontinental and quasi-continental configurations (left column) compared to the region with the lowest residual load standard deviation (Macedonia) and the region with lowest residual load in each continent (analogous to Figure 4).

Supplementary Figure 11. Residual load minimum variability portfolios. Analogous to Supplementary Figure 2.

3. Bias correction factors

ISO	Source	Timespan	Bias
AT	IRENA	2010-19	1.067
BE	ENTSO-E	2015-19	0.765
BG	IRENA	2010-19	1.108
CZ	IRENA	2010-19	1.225
DE	OPSD (1)	2010-19	0.760
DK	ENTSO-E	2015-19	0.718
EE	IRENA	2010-19	0.708
ES	ENTSO-E	2015-19	1.583
FI	IRENA	2010-19	0.948
FR	ENTSO-E	2015-19	0.947
GB	Electric Insights (2)	2010-19	0.700
GR	ENTSO-E	2015-19	1.268
HR	IRENA	2010-19	2.296
HU	IRENA	2010-19	1.143
IE	ENTSO-E	2015-19	1.051
IT	ENTSO-E	2015-19	1.758
LT	IRENA	2010-19	0.906
LU	IRENA	2010-19	0.822
NL	ENTSO-E	2015-19	0.696
NO	ENTSO-E	2015-19	1.013
PL	IRENA	2010-19	0.873
PT	IRENA	2010-19	1.720
RO	IRENA	2010-19	1.282
SE	ENTSO-E	2015-19	1.081

Supplementary Table 1: Bias correction factors, $\frac{CF_{obs}}{CF_{sim}}$, calculated for European countries, which are listed by their ISO2 code. Sources: (1) <https://open-power-system-data.org/data-sources#8> Wind and solar power time series, (2) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.12.037>

Zone	Bias
CN.AH	2.101
CN.BJ	2.286
CN.CQ	4.119
CN.FJ	0.917
CN.GD	1.018
CN.GS	1.037
CN.GX	3.906
CN.GZ	2.642
CN.HA	1.179
CN.HB	1.361
CN.HE	2.389
CN.HL	1.589
CN.HN	3.226
CN.HU	2.914
CN.JL	1.064
CN.JS	0.828
CN.JX	2.667
CN.LN	1.195
CN.NM	1.838
CN.NX	1.431
CN.QH	2.367
CN.SA	2.103
CN.SC	4.320
CN.SD	1.112
CN.SH	0.858
CN.SX	2.291
CN.TJ	1.587
CN.XJ	2.591
CN.XZ	2.153
CN.YN	4.105
CN.ZJ	0.942

Supplementary Table 2: Bias correction factors, $\frac{CF_{obs}}{CF_{sim}}$, calculated for Chinese provinces, which are listed by their HASC_2 code as defined in GADM.

Code	Timespan	Bias
US.AK	2014-19	1.529
US.AZ	2011-19	1.258
US.CA	2010-19	3.021
US.CO	2010-19	1.232
US.HI	2012-19	1.071
US.IA	2010-19	1.057
US.ID	2010-19	1.835
US.IL	2010-19	1.171
US.IN	2010-19	1.019
US.KS	2010-19	1.302
US.MA	2012-19	1.189
US.MD	2012-19	1.370
US.ME	2010-19	1.314
US.MI	2010-19	1.163
US.MN	2010-19	1.016
US.MO	2010-19	0.953
US.MT	2010-19	1.453
US.NC	2017-19	1.479
US.ND	2010-19	1.117
US.NE	2010-19	1.271
US.NH	2010-19	2.058
US.NM	2010-19	1.134
US.NY	2010-19	1.164
US.OH	2013-19	1.003
US.OK	2010-19	1.072
US.OR	2010-19	1.408
US.PA	2010-19	1.456
US.SD	2010-19	1.135
US.TN	2010-19	1.425
US.TX	2010-19	1.012
US.UT	2010-19	1.534
US.VT	2011-19	1.949
US.WA	2010-19	1.859
US.WI	2010-19	1.567
US.WV	2010-19	1.894
US.WY	2010-19	0.977

Supplementary Table 3: Bias correction factors, $\frac{CF_{obs}}{CF_{sim}}$, calculated for US states, which are listed by their HASC_2 code as defined in GADM.

4. Regional configurations and naming conventions

